

Project:

POP-MACHINA

“Collaborative production for the circular economy; a community approach”

Project Acronym: Pop-Machina
Programme: HORIZON2020
Topic: CE-SC5-03-2018
Type of Action: Innovation Action
Start day: 01/06/2019
Duration: 48 months

D8.1 Dissemination, Awareness raising and Communication Plan

ISSUED BY: White Research ISSUE DATE: 28/08/2019 DUE DATE: 31/08/2019

Work Package: Nr. 8

Work Package Leader: White Research

DISSEMINATION LEVEL

PU	Public	v
PP	Restricted to other program participants (including the EC services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the EC Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the EC)	

DOCUMENT HISTORY

Revisions/Amendments

VERSION AND DATE	Changes
V0.1, 10/06/2019	Table of content and overall structure preparation by WR
V0.2, 11/06/2019	Initial version prepared by WR
V0.3, 31/07/2019	Update of the deliverable, prepared by WR
V0.4, 02/08/2019	Internal review of the deliverable
V0.5, 06/08/2019	Updated version of the deliverable for external review
V1.0, 28/08/2019	Final version

LEGAL NOTICE

Neither the European Commission nor any person acting on behalf of the Commission is responsible for the use, which might be made, of the following information.

The views expressed in this report are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Commission.

© **Pop Machina Consortium, 2019**

Reproduction is authorized provided the source is acknowledged

Main authors

- Mr. Alexandros Altsitsiadis, Ms. Anna Piccoli (White Research)

Reviewers

- Ms. Sandra Volders (KU Leuven)

Table of Contents

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	5
1 INTRODUCTION	6
2 ABOUT POP-MACHINA	7
3 DISSEMINATION & COMMUNICATION PLAN	8
3.1 Overview of the plan	8
3.2 Objectives.....	9
3.3 Roles and responsibilities.....	9
4 TARGET AUDIENCES AND TAILORED MESSAGES	11
4.1 The Pop-Machina target audiences	11
4.2 Pop-Machina’s key assets	14
4.3 The Pop-Machina key messages.....	17
4.4 Networks and Multipliers	19
4.5 Synergies with other projects	19
5 COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION TOOLS AND CHANNELS	23
5.1 Promotional material.....	23
5.1.1 Logo	23
5.1.2 Leaflet and Poster	25
5.1.3 Templates	26
5.1.4 Pop-Machina promotional video	26
5.2 Pop-Machina digital presence.....	26
5.2.1 Pop-Machina website.....	26
5.2.2 Newsletter	29
5.3 Social Media Accounts (SMAs)	30
5.3.1 Facebook.....	30
5.3.2 Twitter	31
5.3.3 LinkedIn	32
5.3.4 YouTube.....	33
5.4 Events.....	33
5.4.1 Project events	33
5.4.2 External events and conferences	34

5.5	Publications.....	36
5.5.1	Scientific publications.....	36
5.5.2	Non-scientific publications	37
6	MONITORING, EVALUATION AND REPORTING.....	39
6.1	Monitoring and evaluation	39
6.2	Reporting.....	40
7	TIMELINE AND IMPLEMENTATION PLAN.....	42
8	CONCLUSIONS.....	47
	ANNEXES	48
	ANNEX 1: POP-MACHINA INITIAL DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION GUIDELINES FOR CONSORTIUM PARTNERS	48
1	POP-MACHINA DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION GUIDELINES.....	48
1.1	Main guidelines	48
1.2	Dissemination monitoring tools	49
1.2.1	Pop-Machina Dissemination Reporting Template	49
1.2.2	Pop-Machina Event Reporting Template.....	50
2	WEBSITE AND SOCIAL MEDIA USE GUIDELINES	51
2.1	Guidelines for enhancing Pop-Machina online presence	51
2.1.1	Website.....	51
2.1.2	Social media Accounts	51
	ANNEX 2: DISSEMINATION REPORTING TEMPLATE.....	52
	ANNEX 3: EVENT REPORTING TEMPLATE	53
	ANNEX 4: EXTERNAL CONFERENCES AND EVENTS TEMPLATES.....	55

List of figures

Figure 1.	Overview of the Pop-Machina dissemination and communication strategy	8
Figure 2.	Pop-Machina's target audiences.....	11
Figure 3.	Stakeholder mapping and types of stakeholder engagement.....	12
Figure 4.	Pop-Machina's communication and dissemination activities	23
Figure 5.	Pop-Machina logo	24
Figure 6.	Pop-Machina logo for pilot city	24
Figure 7.	The flag of the European Union.....	24

Figure 8. Colour palette	25
Figure 9. Typeface	25
Figure 10. Mock-up of the Pop-Machina website	27
Figure 11. Snapshot of Pop-Machina's Facebook page	30
Figure 12. Snapshot of Pop-Machina's Twitter account.....	32
Figure 13. Snapshot of Pop-Machina's LinkedIn page.....	32
Figure 14. Snapshot of Pop-Machina's YouTube channel	33
Figure 15. The four stages of dissemination and stakeholder engagement activities	42

List of tables

Table 1. Target audience categories.....	12
Table 2. Interest, communication need and key assets for the targeted audiences	14
Table 3. Pop-Machina baseline messages per stakeholder category.....	18
Table 4. Pop-Machina consortium networks for dissemination	19
Table 5. Indicative list of relevant initiatives for potential synergies.....	20
Table 6. Indicative external conferences and events	35
Table 7. Indicative journals for Pop-Machina	36
Table 8. Overview of the tools to be used to reach different target audiences	38
Table 9. Dissemination plan's targets and indicators.....	39
Table 10. Monitoring and reporting tools for the dissemination and communication activities	40
Table 11. Dissemination phases, goals of each phase and the respective dissemination tools	44
Table 12. GANTT chart of project's communication and awareness raising activities.....	45

Executive summary

This deliverable presents the **Dissemination, Awareness raising and Communication Plan (DACP)** for Pop-Machina, laying out the strategy which will guide the consortium's communication, awareness raising and dissemination efforts that will be carried out during the project's life cycle.

Besides outlining the strategy for it, the document provides an overview of the overall communication, dissemination and awareness raising process, including management and monitoring to ensure the highest possible outreach of the project's activities and results to the relevant audiences. It also describes some of the steps to be taken in cooperation with the organisations involved in other work packages in order to support the effective fulfilment of their objectives.

More precisely, this document includes the following:

- The communication and dissemination **objectives** of the Pop-Machina project;
- The **roles and responsibilities** of the partners with regards to the project's communication and dissemination activities;
- The main **target audiences**, including multipliers and project-relevant networks;
- Examples of **tailored messages** per target audience;
- The **communication channels** and **dissemination tools** that will be used by the consortium partners to increase the project's visibility and public awareness of collaborative production and circular economy and to promote the project's outcomes (i.e. promotional material, social media, website, newsletters, events organised by the project, external events which partners will participate in, scientific and non-scientific publications, synergies with other similar projects and initiatives);
- The **key performance indicators for monitoring and evaluation** of the communication and dissemination activities;
- The **guidelines** and the **reporting templates** of the communication and dissemination activities, which need to be completed by partners throughout the project (event reporting, template for participation in external events/conferences, and the overall dissemination reporting template);
- The **time plan** illustrating the stages of communication, dissemination and stakeholder engagement activities.

All partners are expected to actively participate and contribute in the implementation of the communication and dissemination activities and according to the communication and dissemination strategy, while White Research, as leader of the WP8, will closely monitor the unfolding of the communication and dissemination actions described in this document and provide all the necessary support.

1 Introduction

This document outlines the strategy towards an effective communication of the project's progress and dissemination of project's results and defines the operational framework for the Pop-Machina partners to effectively promote the project, communicate about its activities and disseminate its outcomes.

The overall aim of Pop-Machina's **Dissemination, Awareness raising and Communication Plan (DACP)** is to define tools and actions that contribute to promoting the project's vision, its activities and results among a wide range of stakeholders. The main objective is to guide the consortium in raising awareness of Pop-Machina activities and results by reaching out to defined target groups. This will further help to achieve the successful unfolding of the project, in line with the contractual obligations that the consortium has undertaken with the European Commission. Furthermore, it will support the consortium's efforts towards exploitation and sustainability of the assets developed during the project.

Therefore, this document addresses the core components of an effective dissemination strategy by:

- introducing the different purposes of communication and dissemination activities;
- defining the partners' responsibilities and explaining the allocation of communication and dissemination activities;
- identifying the key target audiences;
- presenting the core messages of the project and outlining the main assets;
- defining the tools and communication channels which will be used to reach the target audiences along with the required actions and resources;
- summarising the internal monitoring, evaluation and reporting of dissemination activities;
- providing an indicative timetable of promotion activities during the life cycle of the project; and
- offering guidelines and templates that can help achieve maximum visibility, thus paving the way for a successful market uptake of the Pop-Machina's results.

Communication and dissemination actions will be carried out throughout the entire duration of the project (M1-M48) aiming at both raising awareness of the project activities and functioning as an additional feedback mechanism that will lead to further refinements of the consortium's work. They will focus on spreading the Pop-Machina messages and results, and engaging stakeholders through a wide range of online and physical tools and channels.

The deployment of the Pop-Machina dissemination strategy will require the active collaboration of all project partners who commit to invest time and resources in reaching out to relevant target audiences, especially at local level (in the seven pilot cities).

It should be noted that both this report and the accompanying guidelines (see Annex 1. Pop-Machina Dissemination and Communication Guidelines) are subject to modifications and updates in line with the project progress and the experience that will be gathered through the various project activities. As such, the dissemination, awareness raising and communication strategy that is presented here is not static. Instead, it will be continuously reviewed in specific time intervals to account for any challenge or opportunity that may arise. An updated version of the DACP is already foreseen for M24, and is expected to build upon the experiences gathered within the first 24 months of Pop-Machina.

2 About Pop-Machina

Pop-Machina aims to combine the maker movement and collaborative production with circular economy, demonstrating the value of circular maker ecosystems for integrated urban planning and development in the EU. Drawing from a number of cutting-edge technologies (factory-of-the-future, blockchain) and disciplines (urban planning, architecture), the project aims to:

- Mobilise citizens under the banner of circular economy and community manufacturing;
- Demonstrate the **effectiveness of circular maker ecosystems and collaborative production** through seven pilot programmes, finally fostering their development at EU level;
- Contribute to the development of an **integrated monitoring and assessment framework** regarding the impacts of maker ecosystems and urban circularity;
- Ultimately, support the implementation of the EU Circular Economy Action Plan by **supporting circular maker ecosystems** and empowering cities to generate circular innovations.

The project unfolds in seven European cities: Santander, Istanbul, Venlo, Thessaloniki, Leuven, Kaunas and Piraeus. In these areas, an elaborate community engagement programme will be developed to stimulate existing maker communities and create new ones through maker fairs, events and incentive schemes (e.g. tokenisation). Suitable spaces will be identified for the communities to use and makers will also be provided with the tools needed to use materials according to the principles of circularity. Besides, tailored training programmes in circular collaborative production will be developed, with a focus on women and vulnerable groups, which will empower citizens' skills and creativity, and will provide business development services to promising entrepreneurs. Additionally, the project will strengthen policy discussion on tax and legal barriers that hamper collaborative production through policy events.

By designing and implementing a novel urban development framework which draws from innovative urban planning approaches and social and industry 4.0 technologies, Pop-Machina supports the seven pilot cities in generating circular innovations and creating products and services in a sustainable way, thus contributing to reduce waste and environmental footprint of urban consumption.

Ultimately, Pop-Machina's development framework, along with its visions and circular solutions, is expected to pave the way towards the adoption of circular maker ecosystems across European cities beyond the seven pilot areas.

3 Dissemination & Communication Plan

The Pop-Machina DACP has been developed in order to facilitate the achievement of the project's objectives. Hence, it defines a clear strategy and the related operational framework taking the objectives and actions mentioned in Chapter 2 into account and covering the entire project duration. Therefore, it will function as a horizontal document that is connected to all parts of the project workplan and its respective activities.

3.1 Overview of the plan

The Pop-Machina DACP is based on a clear strategy for communication and dissemination activities that builds upon the main project's concepts (e.g. collaborative production, maker movement, circular economy, urban planning, Factory of the Future, etc.) to ensure that the overall objectives are achieved. The strategy is translated into an actionable plan by considering multiple key elements as illustrated in the figure below and described in more detail in the next chapters.

Figure 1. Overview of the Pop-Machina dissemination and communication strategy¹

To ensure successful outcomes, the communication and dissemination strategy is translated into a practical and realistic plan from the beginning, paying attention to defining the details of the elements shown above at a very early stage, including the appropriate tools, channels and actions to engage the target audiences. However, the plan remains flexible and open to changes when necessary. At regular intervals, all the key elements for successful communication and dissemination will be reviewed, notably: **what should be communicated** (project concepts, outcomes and assets) and **why, to whom** (target groups), **by what means** (tools, channels, etc.), and **when**.

¹ Inspired by Fig.1 of: Gaillard, M., and N. Germain, "Deliverable 9.2 – Dissemination and communication plan", DTOceanPlus, France Energies Marines, 10 December 2018, p.10.

3.2 Objectives

Communications and dissemination should raise awareness about the project and give visibility to events and activities, paving the way for the effective promotion of the project's vision, its actual unfolding and its results among a wide range of stakeholders and, consequently, contributing to the success of the different work packages as well as the exploitation of Pop-Machina's outcomes. Thus, the main aim of the strategy is to enable a wide approach and to support the positive impact of the project, both exploiting the knowledge within the consortium and transferring knowledge created in the project further to interested stakeholders. This strategy already embeds a plan, which defines clear guidelines for all the communication and dissemination activities that will be carried out throughout the project, including all operational elements.

Overall, the Pop-Machina communication and dissemination strategy has a number of high-level objectives which are the following:

- Encourage people to join the maker communities;
- Empower local vulnerable groups;
- Encourage policy makers to embrace collaborative production and circular economy;
- Introduce the makers movement in the EU's circular economy.

Besides that, Pop-Machina's strategy includes several other operational objectives that will help the consortium to reach its strategic goals. They are listed below:

- Promote the project's concept, activities, and events to interested target groups and stakeholders;
- Enhance people's awareness of the project's goals and assets;
- Encourage involvement in the project's activities;
- Encourage participation in relevant conferences and other events;
- Disseminate the project's results and collected knowledge to the public;
- Establish liaisons and synergies with other relevant initiatives;
- Foster an open policy dialogue.

All communication and dissemination activities will be therefore focused on:

- **Raising awareness:** by informing all interested parties about the project's objectives, results, benefits, use and applicability through various channels. This should also lead to additional awareness raising through "word of mouth", which will further help the sustainability of the project.
- **Promoting a deeper understanding:** by engaging with selected audiences which can directly benefit from the project's activities and tools as well as by engaging with target groups in order to facilitate adoption of the project's outcomes.
- **Influencing decision-making:** by showcasing evidence from the project activities in order to influence and "bring change" within authorities and policy makers regarding the uptake of the maker movement as well as collaborative production practices.

3.3 Roles and responsibilities

In order to achieve the aims and objectives of the communication and dissemination plan, all team members of the consortium will play a key role during Pop-Machina's communication activities. Partners' contribution will be a natural by-product of the project's development as most activities, results, milestones and progress will either involve stakeholder engagement and communication or turn into assets that should be adequately promoted. Partners naturally contribute to offline

communication by organising events and raising awareness of the project locally. Furthermore, partners are expected to help enhance the online presence of Pop-Machina by providing content for the website and the project's social media accounts. This contribution can be anything, from a Facebook post to an article describing a Pop-Machina dissemination activity, with the goal of creating a constant flow of content regarding the project's actions.

Finally, partners are welcome to pursue the widest possible exposure of the project through their participation in relevant events/conferences and through publications for online/offline sources of information (e.g. websites, newspapers, magazines, etc.).

At the end of each project semester, all partners are required to present the main dissemination actions they carried out during the semester, by filling in the Dissemination Reporting template (Annex 2). Dissemination actions mentioned in this template could be the organisation of event, participation to event, informal meetings, interviews, communication campaign (e.g. newsletter send outs, leaflets, etc.), publications, training, other. Filled-in templates will help keep track of the project's outreach.

Along with the Dissemination Reporting template partners are asked to complete the Event Reporting template (Annex 3) for each event that they organised or participated in during the semester, presenting the main dissemination actions that took place in that specific event. Such reports will feed in the continuous update of the website and help monitor stakeholder engagement at local level.

4 Target audiences and tailored messages

In order to achieve the objectives indicated in Chapter 3.2, it is essential to decide on the audiences, messages, methods and timing of the communication and dissemination.

4.1 The Pop-Machina target audiences

As shown in Figure 2, Pop-Machina has multiple audiences who have different needs and interests. Hence, communication must be targeted appropriately in order to be effective.

Figure 2. Pop-Machina's target audiences

To do so, a Stakeholders Classification Model² will be followed to identify the main target audiences of the project. This model will be further elaborated in the frame of the second version of this strategy (M24) and will build upon the experience gathered by then to define a number of parameters for each identified stakeholder group such as:

- The power of each stakeholder (level of stakeholder's authority)
- The interest in the project outcomes
- The level of active participation in the project
- The ability to change parts of the project planning and outcomes (stakeholder's influence).

² Emerson Wagner Mainardes, Helena Alves, Mário Raposo, (2012) "A model for stakeholder classification and stakeholder relationships", *Management Decision*, Vol. 50 Issue: 10, pp.1861-1879.

As a matter of fact, the type of communication and the message conveyed change depending on the level of interest and the influence of a certain group of stakeholders as well as on the impact that the project (or one of its activity) has on that group, as illustrated in the simple diagrams below.

Figure 3. Stakeholder mapping and types of stakeholder engagement

At this stage, the stakeholder groups that are illustrated in the table below have been identified as relevant to Pop-Machina and, thus, represent the target audiences of communication and dissemination. These groups cover several stakeholder categories across different regions. This list of target stakeholder might be adapted based on collected project experience and actual data as well as based on the specificities of each pilot area.

Table 1. Target audience categories

Target Group	Description	Example of stakeholders
Cities, Regions & National authorities	All national authorities that are involved into each city or region and are potentially interested in improving their urban development strategies, as adopters of the circular collaborative production schemes proposed by the project.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> City, regional & national authorities Municipalities Counties
Makers / Maker communities	All individuals who create things, often using materials or re-assembly products that are discarded, broken or unused/underused and can have a role in relation to the project.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Individual makers Fab Lab communities DIY communities Maker groups Artisans Supporters of the maker movement
Industry	Private industrial sector stakeholders who are the main technology and service providers, and with a focus on circular production.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Raw material suppliers Technology solutions and services providers Suppliers of 3D printers Logistics providers Waste management companies

Target Group	Description	Example of stakeholders
Circular Entrepreneurs & Investors	Private enterprises interested in circular economy (e.g. eco-product design production, etc.), as well as financing actors searching for investments in this field aiming to increase market potential for circular solutions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Green start-ups • Businesses creating circular innovations • Accelerators • Incubators
Policy makers	Decision-makers, EU and national level stakeholders, as well as the relevant licensing authorities, playing a key role in policy design, adoption and implementation (especially in the fields of climate and energy, but also culture, creativity and inclusive society).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decision-makers • Relevant licensing authorities • National agencies relevant to sustainable cities, urban planning, environmental management, energy efficiency, etc. • EC, European Environment Agency, European Institute of Innovation and Technology, European Energy Network
Academic community	The academic community as a whole, with a focus on urban planning experts, sustainability and circular economy researchers. This target group also covers researchers at universities and other research institutions working in a range of other disciplines (e.g. behavioural and social sciences, environmental sciences, technical fields).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Universities and research centres • Urban planning experts • Sustainability & circular economy researchers • Diverse research groups, experts and educators in: smart cities, environmental sciences, social sciences, behavioural research, relevant ICT, etc.
Civil society	All NGOs and other interested groups (Non-for-profit organisations, civil society groups, local associations, etc.) related to ecology, sustainability, urban resilience, social inclusion and cohesion, as well as manufacturing, adult learning and handicrafts that are active within the urban ecosystem.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developmental NGOs • Community groups • Women's organisations • Professional associations • Trade unions • Social movements
General public	All citizens who can potentially have a role in relation to the project and especially vulnerable groups of the local population.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General public • Women • Migrants • Elderly • Children • People with disabilities
Relevant EU projects	Both ongoing and completed European projects which are focusing on similar topics including among other: circular economy, sustainable urbanisation, nature-based solutions, collaborative production.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevant European projects (e.g. CLEVER Cities, NATURVATION, Nature4Cities, ENSUGI, MAtchUP, STARDUST, etc.)
Major EU Initiatives	Major European as well as International Initiatives that are relevant to the project's advances and outputs.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European & International Initiatives • Covenant of Mayors for the Climate and Energy • Global Platform for Sustainable Cities
End-users	Individuals interested in the project's outcomes who may use the products, services and infrastructures developed during the project.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Customers • End-users • Prosumers

Each of the above-mentioned audiences is associated with specific communications, marketing or dissemination objectives. Therefore, each group has a stake in different project assets, as illustrated in the next section.

4.2 Pop-Machina's key assets

The Pop-Machina project will have specific assets that can be of interest for the different stakeholder categories. Although the assets will be defined based on the actual project activities, a preliminary list of core assets is the following:

- The Pop-Machina novel urban development framework
- The Pop-Machina Circular Maker Communities
- The Pop-Machina Circular Makerspaces
- Training on collaborative production
- Pop-Machina Maker Academy
- Pop-Machina Policy Recommendation and Uptake Guide
- The integrated social collaboration platform
- The online inventory of circular maker solutions
- Business support services
- Circular product/service prototypes developed and demonstrated by the communities
- The Monitoring and Impact Assessment Framework
- The Blockchain-as-a-Service (BaaS) mechanism
- Tokenisation and incentivisation technologies and insights
- The Pop-Machina Accelerator
- Policy recommendations
- The Pop-Machina Integration Guide

To work effectively with all stakeholders, it is needed to have a good knowledge of their needs. The following table illustrates the main role and interest of the different subgroups in relation to deployment of Pop-Machina solutions and the need for communication.

Table 2. Interest, communication need and key assets for the targeted audiences

Audience	Interest in Pop-Machina	Communication need	Key assets
Cities, Regions & National authorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide better services to citizen • Promote inclusion • Incentivise local economy and local production • Promote what makes the city unique and sustainable 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Get detailed information about what Pop-Machina has to offer, its opportunities and applications • Get information about the assessment of the pilot experience • Get access to varied communities of stakeholders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • novel urban development frameworks that can be applied in order to address socio-economic and environmental challenges and contribute to local circular collaborative economy • local Circular Maker Communities and Makerspaces • circular product/service prototypes developed and demonstrated by the communities • Pop-Machina Integration Guide
Makers / Maker communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Get inspired from Pop-Machina to boost innovation and stimulate prototype development 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Get information about Pop-Machina's tools and concepts • Get information about the possibility of taking part in 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • new ways and tools of collaborative production • integrated social collaboration platform

Audience	Interest in Pop-Machina	Communication need	Key assets
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Become familiar with principles of circular economy to innovate their production practices • Get access to spaces, tools and other stakeholders to enhance their creation process 	<p>local maker programmes and other Pop-Machina's events and services, to co-create and share knowledge, as well as acquire new one</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Blockchain-as-a-Service (BaaS) mechanism • tokenisation and incentivisation schemes • Pop-Machina Accelerator • tailored training on collaborative production • access to the Maker Academy • access to business support services • Pop-Machina Integration Guide
Industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leverage the Pop-Machina Maker Communities and tools and market their products/services • Try real environment implementation for their product/services • 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Get information about the Pop-Machina circular maker ecosystem as moving beyond the state of the art and integration aspects • Communicate the advantages of industry participation in the circular maker production • Get information about Pop-Machina vision and approach to provide the best support 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • access to Maker Communities who may benefit from industry products or bring in innovation in traditional processes • online inventory of circular maker solutions • Pop-Machina's results that can be used to generate business, demonstrate and scale their prototypes and services
Circular Entrepreneurs & Investors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use the Pop-Machina tools, technology and framework to quickly develop new circular innovations • Promote their business models • Follow pilot activities, provide consultancy and support the project's progress 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Receive information about tools and guidelines and how to use them • Be informed about the potential of other application areas • Get information about the activities that can take part in to co-create and share knowledge, as well as acquire new one 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pop-Machina's results that can be used to generate business and make profitable innovations • access to local Circular Maker Communities and Makerspaces • integrated social collaboration platform • online inventory of circular maker solutions • Blockchain-as-a-Service (BaaS) mechanism
Policy makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify the benefits and opportunities of implementing circular economy solutions within the city ecosystem • Identify gaps on the implementation of collaborative production in the urban development context and potential impacts that this will have in the citizens' life 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Get introduced to Pop-Machina and the collaborative production opportunities for circular economy and sustainable solutions implementation • Get information about the results from the pilots, especially with regard to the regulatory landscape • Get information about barriers that hinder further 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • evidence collected through pilots • Pop-Machina Policy Recommendation and Uptake Guide • online inventory of circular maker solutions • Tokenisation and incentivisation schemes • Policy recommendations • Pop-Machina Integration Guide

Audience	Interest in Pop-Machina	Communication need	Key assets
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify barriers to the creation of a circular maker ecosystem within urban context Make and implement informed and high-quality impactful decisions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> uptake of collaborative production approaches Obtain evidence to make informed decision about relevant policies and measures in the creation of a circular maker ecosystem 	
Academic community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify areas for further research and innovation collect evidence about circular collaborative production and facilitate the uptake of best practices Build and exchange knowledge of circular economy, sustainability and collaborative production 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Get introduced to Pop-Machina and its innovations, moving beyond state of the art Get information about scientific progress and innovation developed during the project 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pop-Machina's results which they can use for their own research online inventory of circular maker solutions Monitoring and Impact Assessment Framework Blockchain-as-a-Service (BaaS) mechanism Tokenisation and incentivisation schemes Pop-Machina Integration Guide
Civil society	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> become aware of communities that pursue similar goals as well as practices and tools they can leverage to achieve their objectives Solve issues of pollution and waste concern to promote the sustainability of the community 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Get information about Pop-Machina as regards issues relevant to citizens' daily life and society in general Get information about Pop-Machina in terms of citizens' involvement Get information about Pop-Machina applications and their context in terms of pros and cons Enter into dialogue with policy makers and be heard 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> findings about the impact and benefits of collaborative production and circular economy for the society access to local Circular Maker Communities and Makerspaces online inventory of circular maker solutions circular product/service prototypes developed and demonstrated by the communities Tokenisation and incentivisation schemes Pop-Machina Integration Guide
General public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Become aware of the project's aim and relevance Become familiar with principles of circular economy and innovative production practices Develop skills 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Get information about Pop-Machina as regards issues relevant to citizens' daily life and society in general Get information about Pop-Machina applications and their context in terms of pros and cons Get information about the activities that can take part in to co-create and share knowledge, as well as acquire new one 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> information about collaborative production, circular economy possibility to join tailored training access to local Circular Maker Communities and Makerspaces online inventory of circular maker solutions Circular product/service prototypes developed and demonstrated by the communities

Audience	Interest in Pop-Machina	Communication need	Key assets
Relevant EU projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Exchange knowledge and collaborate to maximise the benefits of the respective projects across Europe 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Get introduced to Pop-Machina, its approach and objectives and identify opportunities for collaboration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> access to knowledge and stakeholders Pop-Machina Integration Guide Pop-Machina Policy Recommendation and Uptake Guide Monitoring and Impact Assessment Framework Tokenisation and incentivisation schemes
Major EU Initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Exchange knowledge and collaborate Utilise the Pop-Machina results Promote socio-economic and environmental benefits of EU-funded initiatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Get introduced to Pop-Machina, its approach and objectives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> access to knowledge and stakeholders Pop-Machina Integration Guide Pop-Machina Policy Recommendation and Uptake Guide Monitoring and Impact Assessment Framework Tokenisation and incentivisation schemes
End-users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Get access to innovative solutions that can meet their needs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Get information about Pop-Machina's applications and their context in terms of pros and cons Test the products developed by local makers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> information about collaborative production, circular economy final products manufactured from the Maker Communities

Having a clear overview of the project assets is crucial not only for elaborating targeted and effective messages, but also for defining ways to make the project and its findings sustainable and exploitable beyond its official duration. Consequently, project assets will be explored in further detail in the frame of the Innovation, Exploitation and Sustainability Plan (D8.3, M12).

4.3 The Pop-Machina key messages

A critical part of an effective communication and dissemination plan is to define not only the key audiences and their assets, but also the core messages that will be communicated to the target audiences. Considering their different needs and their stake in different project's assets, the various stakeholder groups will be targeted through different messages, as outlined in the table below. Depending on the audience they address, the messages can either promote project assets/outcomes or invite stakeholders' participation in the project (e.g. invitation to project events, request for input and/or validation). Clearly, in order to respond to the specific of the Pop-Machina's stakeholders, these messages will be refined over the course of the project and more messages will be added based on the experience gathered during the project. An updated list will be presented in the second version of this plan (M24).

Table 3. Pop-Machina baseline messages per stakeholder category

Target groups	Key message
Cities & Regions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pop-Machina makes cities more sustainable by fostering resource efficiency, limiting waste and reducing the environmental footprint of urban consumption. • Pop-Machina gives life to underused buildings by transforming them into makerspaces. • Pop-Machina upscales makerspaces to key vectors of circular sustainable urbanisation.
Makers / Maker communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pop-Machina offers opportunities for learning and developing new skills and capabilities. • Pop-Machina provides makers with access to spaces, tools and methods to support collaborative production and circular economy. • Pop-Machina offers business support for promising circular innovations.
Industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Results generated by Pop-Machina may open new market opportunities. • Pop-Machina can test and unlock new technology-based services and open the way of their exploitation.
Circular Entrepreneurs & Investors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Through the circular maker ecosystems, Pop-Machina can create economic value, generating new business and making profitable circular innovations. • Pop-Machina uses tools, technology and frameworks to quickly develop new circular innovations.
Policy makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pop-Machina supports the implementation of EU Circular Economy Action Plan. • Pop-Machina contributes to future evidence-based policy making in the field of sustainable circular maker ecosystems.
Academic community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pop-Machina provides new knowledge on circular economy and sustainability. • Pop-Machina aims to develop novel Urban Planning Framework, as well as an Impact Assessment framework taking into account the needs, goals and specificities of the urban environment.
Civil society	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pop-Machina provides tested methods for stakeholder engagement and monitoring and assessment. • Pop-Machina provides a collaborative production experience that is inclusive, sustainable and tailored to citizens' needs. • Pop-Machina results can improve urban production and consumption systems.
General public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pop-Machina offers opportunities for learning and developing new skills and capabilities. • Pop-Machina empowers consumers to re-assembly products that are discarded, broken or unused.
Relevant EU projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Projects with similar goals should liaise with one another and with Pop-Machina since combined efforts have more chances of success. • Through Pop-Machina new solutions will be envisioned by combining results and findings from different initiatives.
Major EU Initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pop-Machina raises awareness on collaborative production and relative tools at European level. • Through Pop-Machina new solutions may be envisioned by combining results and findings from different initiatives.
End-users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pop-Machina will introduce new products and/or services into the market. • Pop-Machina enables consumers to re-assembly products that are discarded, broken or unused regardless of their specific background or skillset.

The different communication materials will provide different levels of detail, depending on the purpose and/or the target group they serve. Detailed descriptions of the respective communication channels and activities planned can be found in subsequent chapters of this strategy.

4.4 Networks and Multipliers

The strategic use of networks and other communication multipliers is considered essential to the success of the Pop-Machina communications and dissemination effort. Key targets in this context include several high-impact initiatives, relevant academic communities and respective stakeholders. The following table provides an initial list of some key European initiatives and networks that are relevant to the project's progress and outputs and could help achieve maximum visibility and outreach.

Table 4. Pop-Machina consortium networks for dissemination

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Covenant of Mayors • European Innovation Partnership in Smart Cities & Communities (EIP-SCC) • European Innovation Partnership on Raw Materials • EUROCITIES • CIVITAS Initiative • Climate KIC (EU climate innovation initiative) • CEMR (Council of European Municipalities and Regions) • Metrex (Network of European Metropolitan Regions & Areas) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Urban Innovative Actions (UIA) • Enterprise Europe Network (EEN) • Sustainable Public Procurement Global Cities Network • The Spanish Network of Smart Cities (SNSC) <i>(led by Santander)</i> • Urban Agenda Partnership on Circular Economy group <i>(Kaunas is a member)</i> • NESTA (Innovation Foundation) • "Let's do it world" network • EuroHealthNet
---	--

In addition to the previous consortium partners' networks, Pop-Machina will focus on bringing together relevant stakeholders not only to disseminate the project results, but also to develop an interactive **Network of Interest**, aiming at discussing challenges and opportunities arising in the circular maker communities. To do so, a separate task within the project's workplan has been foreseen. Through Pop-Machina's Network of Interest and by using a multi-actor engagement approach for all work packages, Pop-Machina will reach both scientific and broad audiences covering scientific, policy, commercial as well as socio-economic aspects.

Overall, the list of networks and multipliers will be continually enriched throughout the course of the project. These networks will be targeted with strategic communications such as press releases, major project announcements and event notifications. In addition, the events and activities organised by these organisations will be leveraged, when possible, to promote the Pop-Machina project.

4.5 Synergies with other projects

Communication with other similar regional, national and EU projects and initiatives will be established from the very early stages of the project implementation, aiming not only to create potential synergies, but also benefit from their experience and knowledge and maximise the impact of Pop-Machina's communication activities in an efficient way, by leveraging multiplier and network effects with a "win-win" perspective.

Collaborations with respect to joint dissemination activities (especially with relevant EU funded projects) will be sought. This could take the following forms:

- Mutual reference of projects on respective websites;
- Mutual support through social media accounts;

- Exchange of news, invitations to external events, press releases and further dissemination actions through social media communication channels;
- Participation in events of similar projects;
- Explore possibility to co-organise event;
- Invitations to participate in Pop-Machina's events.

Other occasions for joint efforts may emerge during the project duration and will be described in the updated version of this document (M24).

The nature of the collaboration will be decided based on discussions with the representatives of the respective projects. All partners will contribute to identifying relevant projects at local level. Projects and initiatives which Pop-Machina partners already participate in or have easy access to may represent a first sample to be used for possible synergies. An indicative selection of relevant initiatives is provided below.

Table 5. Indicative list of relevant initiatives for potential synergies

Initiative	Brief description	End	Countries
CIRCuIT	CIRCuIT (H2020) aims at demonstrating three innovative solutions in four European cities: dismantle buildings to reuse materials; transformation and refurbishment; and design for disassembly and flexible construction, thus supporting the implementation of circular construction solutions.	2023	Denmark, UK, Germany, Finland
CityLoops	CityLoops (H2020) brings together six ambitious European cities to demonstrate a series of innovative tools and urban planning approaches, aimed at closing the loops of urban material flows and increasing their regenerative capacity.	2023	Spain, Norway, Denmark, Portugal, Netherlands, Germany, Finland, Belgium,
REFLOW	REFLOW (H2020) is an interdisciplinary cross-sectoral European Training Network combining world-leading scientists and key stake-holders in dairy processing, fertilizer production and phosphorous recycling with early stage researchers to address important technical and socio-economic challenges associated with the recovery of phosphorous from dairy processing waste water and its recycling into fertilizer products enabling sustainable expansion of the dairy industry in Europe.	2022	Ireland, Spain, Poland, Belgium, France, Sweden, Denmark, Germany, Italy, UK, Netherlands
CITIES-4-PEOPLE	Cities-4-People (H2020) deploys a community-driven pilot programme in five cities helping citizens, city authorities and innovation experts work together to define urban and peri-urban challenges, co-design sustainable solutions, put them to the test in and scale the more potent ones.	2020	UK, Hungary, Germany, Greece, Turkey, Belgium, Netherlands
FORCE	FORCE (H2020) aims at minimising the leakage of materials from the linear economy and works towards a circular economy via local partnerships that target one of four materials: plastic waste, strategic metals from electronic and electric equipment, surplus food and biowaste, and wood waste.	2020	Denmark, Germany, Portugal, Italy

Initiative	Brief description	End	Countries
eDREAM	eDREAM (H2020) provides a novel near real time DR scalable secure blockchain-driven tech and business framework to optimize aggregated system services flexibility provisioning to DSOs.	2020	Italy, Greece, UK, Spain, Romania,
WASTE4Think	WASTE4Think (H2020) aims at advancing the current waste management practices into a circular economy motto, demonstrating a set of 20 eco-innovative solutions that cover all the waste value chain, with the help of citizen participation in order to build more sustainable, eco-friendly cities.	2019	Spain, Greece, Denmark, Italy, Germany, Portugal,
Factory2Fit	Factory2Fit (H2020) aspires to make more attractive, inclusive and safe manufacturing jobs by providing workers a leading role in adapting their own job tasks based on their characteristics.	2019	Finland, Ireland, Greece, Germany
KONFIDO	KONFIDO (H2020) employs a holistic approach to advance the state of the art in eHealth technology with respect to four key dimensions of digital security, namely: (i) data preservation, (ii) data access and modification, (iii) data exchange, as well as (iv) interoperability and compliance.	2019	UK, Greece, Italy, France, Belgium, Spain, Denmark,
SIMPLA	SIMPLA (H2020) supports local authorities in harmonising their SEAPs and SUMP. It offers dedicated training and coaching, based on a sound methodology devised at transnational level, with a view to enabling the joint development of sustainable energy and mobility plans.	2019	Italy, Austria, Spain, Bulgaria, Croatia, Romania
ISABEL	ISABEL (H2020) is aimed at creating and supporting communities to build sustainable biogas initiatives via services (e.g. techno-economic analyses, environment impact assessments, etc.) as well as digital and non-digital tools underpinned by social innovation and public participation.	2018	Greece, France, Germany, UK, Belgium
OrganiCity	OrganiCity (H2020) aims to foster co-creation in smart cities and provide a platform for experimentation (EaaS) in the cities.	2018	Denmark, UK, Spain, Sweden, Greece, France, Germany, Australia
Prosperity4all	Prosperity4all (FP7) offers an ICT infrastructure that can enable the growth of an ecosystem that is based on self-rewarding collaboration and can reduce redundant development, lower costs, increase market reach and penetration at international level.	2018	Germany, UK, Austria, Belgium, Canada, Italy, Switzerland, Cyprus, Greece, Denmark, Spain, Ireland, Sweden
MAKE-IT	MAKE-IT (H2020) focused on the role of CAPS in the growth and governance of the maker movement, especially in relation to IT, using and creating social innovations and achieving sustainability. It offers several meaningful results such as insights, videos and software tools.	2017	Netherlands, Denmark, Austria, Germany, Spain, Croatia, Estonia,
SatisFactory	SatisFactory (H2020) contributes to the transformation of traditional industrial environments into Industry 4.0 using cutting-edge technologies in ways that are both productive and appealing to youth.	2017	Greece, France, Germany, Italy, Switzerland

Overall, the Pop-Machina consortium acknowledges that its dissemination strategy cannot reach its full potential unless collaboration with similar projects is established. Therefore, the project partners

will continuously identify such projects/initiatives and ask for necessary data, including the key-persons to be contacted (i.e. coordinators and/or dissemination managers) in order to discuss opportunities for potential synergies and coordinate actions. All efforts in this direction will be described by the respective partners in the progress reports that will be prepared at the end of each project semester.

5 Communication and dissemination tools and channels

The dissemination and communication strategy will be implemented using a combination of channels and tools to maximise the chances of success, depending on the messages to be distributed and the dissemination objectives to be achieved, as illustrated below:

Figure 4. Pop-Machina's communication and dissemination activities

The expected use of communication and dissemination channels by the consortium is described in the dedicated guidelines (Annex 1). A more detailed description of each channel is provided in the next sub-sections.

5.1 Promotional material

White Research and KU Leuven are responsible for the preparation of the graphic design and content of all printable promotional materials of Pop-Machina, while city partners are responsible for translations and adaptations (if considered necessary) and printing according to its specific needs.

The promotional material of the project will be mainly used at the project's warm-up events, during workshops and in external events which partners will participate in. It will also be available online for download. The promotional material will be characterised by a recognisable visual identity, as indicated in further detail below.

5.1.1 Logo

A project logo and the visual identity have been developed (by M2) in order to satisfy the graphic requirements of the project. The logo is expected to make the project recognisable and represents the basis for the design of all the promotional material (e.g. leaflets, posters, newsletters, deliverables, social media, website, publications, publicity for internal and external events, etc.).

During the kick-off meeting of the project, various logo options were presented to the partners in order to state their preferences and select their favourite design. The selected logo of Pop-Machina was adopted in agreement with all partners and it is presented below.

Figure 5. Pop-Machina logo

The design of the logo reminds of circular economy thanks to the concentric circles. This also suggests a spill-over effect which characterises bottom-up dynamics, which are at the core of collaborative production and the maker movement. The green dots, besides fostering environmentally-friendly connections, represent initiatives of local stakeholders. Last, but not least, the alternation of lines and dots hints at cross-pollination. In other to strengthen the project's identity at local level, each pilot city will have a dedicated logo, meaning that the general logo will be integrated using the name of the specific city, as shown in the example below.

Figure 6. Pop-Machina logo for pilot city

In addition to the Pop-Machina logo, in any communication material, deliverable, presentation, etc. produced in the frame of the project, the EU flag will be shown.

Figure 7. The flag of the European Union

The EU flag will be always accompanied by the following statement: *"Pop-Machina has received funding from the European Union' Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 821479"*.

To strengthen the visual identity of the project, a specific colour scheme should be followed. The logo colour scheme is illustrated below.

	RGB	HEX
	160, 191, 56	#a0bf38
	49, 88, 160	#3158a0

Figure 8. Colour palette

Additionally, partners will be invited to use the logo typeface for their promotional materials whenever possible to ensure consistency and further reinforce the visual identity of the project.

LETTERTYPE LOGO: Arch

Lettertype: Brandon (Regular, Medium, Bold)

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxy
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 0123456789

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxy
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 0123456789

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxy
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 0123456789

Figure 9. Typeface

5.1.2 Leaflet and Poster

Leaflets and posters are important tools to support the dissemination and communication activities of Pop-Machina and attract the interest of the various target audiences.

The leaflet will be produced latest by M6 and it will introduce the Pop-Machina's concept and approach, its objectives, expected results, and include key contact details and the overview of the consortium. Apart from the final English version, the Pop-Machina leaflet will be translated in other national languages of the project pilot cities (Lithuanian, Greek, Spanish, Turkish, Dutch) by local partners, if deemed necessary. The Pop-Machina poster will also be developed latest by M6 and will illustrate basic information of the project's vision and approach, including visual elements, to catch the attention of the audience. The draft versions of the project leaflet and poster will be modified based on the comments collected from the project coordinator and the partners.

Both promotional materials will provide information about the partners involved, together with the project's contact, website and SMAs details and will acknowledge the funding that the project receives through the Horizon 2020 programme. Both leaflet and poster will be available in downloadable electronic form on the Pop-Machina website. Furthermore, hard copies will be available for distribution at the various events that will be organised in the frame of the project. They will also be distributed at external events which partners will participate to.

The final version of the project leaflet and the poster will be included in the updated version of this deliverable (M24).

5.1.3 Templates

In order to facilitate partners' communication and dissemination activities and to ensure consistency in terms of visual identity, several templates are under preparation, notably:

- The Pop-Machina presentation template for new presentations;
- Project deliverables and reports template (external and internal).

In addition to the above-mentioned templates, a Pop-Machina letterhead is also being developed. This project letterhead will be used for various project activities, and especially for agendas and official invitations to events.

Moreover, a PowerPoint presentation providing an overview of the project will be created and shared both with the European Commission as requested during the kick-off meeting and with all partners. Such a presentation will be used to describe the main elements and activities of the project during, for example, external events, without requiring partners to develop a presentation from scratch every time.

The final versions of the presentation template, the publication template and the letterhead will be included in the next version of this deliverable (M24).

5.1.4 Pop-Machina promotional video

A promotional video will be produced (in M6) to raise awareness and to exploit viral effects. The video will be uploaded to the project's YouTube channel, the project's website and will be shared on the other SMAs as well, aiming to enhance the visibility of the project to the greatest extent possible. This short video will give an overview of the project and its objectives, possibly showcasing the main approaches and pilot actions that will be developed during Pop-Machina project. The video duration will be limited in order to keep the viewer's attention and the use of language will be minimised to ensure access to an international audience who may not necessarily be familiar with English.

5.2 Pop-Machina digital presence

5.2.1 Pop-Machina website

The website is a key communication tool to increase the project's visibility and impact, presenting the progress of the project to wider audiences. The Pop-Machina website will be launched latest at the end of M6 of the project. Rather than targeting one specific audience, the website will be a living repository of project's information and news which will serve as the online platform for reaching out to stakeholders at large. The structure and content of the website will be designed to ensure ease of use and will clearly report the project's concept and objectives, but also contain relevant information about its progress, with news and event announcements.

KU Leuven is the partner responsible for the development, maintenance, and technical management of the website, while White Research is in charge of web editing and content development. Should there be any changes in the allocation of responsibilities, they will be duly indicated in the updated version of the Dissemination and Communication Plan. The website will be built in Plone environment. Special attention will be paid to a type of website that is responsive and accessible via and compatible with a variety of devices, including mobile ones.

Besides the key information which will be presented, the website will encompass all publishable project's outcomes, including promotional material, reports, publications, deliverables and further resources of interest. The website will reflect the work happening in the context of Pop-Machina, and especially the progress in the development of the maker communities in the seven pilot areas, along with real-life examples of testing Pop-Machina's approaches and tools. All partners are, hence, expected to contribute to the content development process with news and updates as well as with the translation of the content when relevant to local communities. The website will regularly be updated and report on project's pilot activities, internal and external events, findings, publishable outcomes, information about partners and similar projects/initiatives, as well as other news that are relevant to the project and its development.

At the current stage, a **draft architecture** of the website has been conceptualised, while the final structure will be presented in the updated version of the project's dissemination and communication strategy plan (M24). The mock-up of the website is illustrated below:

Figure 10. Mock-up of the Pop-Machina website

The indicative sitemap is as follows:

- **Home page** (Static). It will display:
 - A sentence summarising the objective of the project: an internal link to the **About** section
 - An internal link to:
 - What is Pop-Machina about
 - Pop-Machina Circular Maker communities
 - Pop-Machina Research: an internal link inviting to explore the main outcomes of the project (e.g. link to Resources)

- “Pop-Machina in action”: an overview of the 7 pilot areas (e.g. a map with coloured areas), linking to the “Pilot areas” page
- A section that monitors updates for Social Media hashtags that are relevant to the project (e.g. Pop-Machina Tweets: main Twitter window linking back to the Twitter platform)
- Calendar: an internal link to Events. It would be possible to visualise upcoming and past events in a calendar with different colours
- “Follow us and share”: main social media icons linking back to the Pop-Machina SMAs (preferably at the right top of the homepage)
- A button that will invite visitors to register to our newsletter. Through this button, their email address will be automatically included in a dedicated listserv created by KU Leuven
- Overview of project partner’s logos
- Pop-Machina logo, EU logo and disclaimer
- Privacy policy
- Contact: pop-machina@kuleuven.be

- **About** (Static). It will include the following information:
 - About – small summary of the project. Internal links to the Concept and Approach page, as well as Pop-Machina pilot cases
 - Concept and approach – description of the Pop-Machina concept and the main pillars on which it is build
 - Pop-Machina Goals – description of the project’s objectives
 - Activities – description of the project’s main activities (e.g. training programmes)
 - Consortium – divided into: Partners (with link to their websites) and Advisory Board

- **The social collaboration platform**. It will include the following information:
 - What tools are offered through the platform
 - Guidelines & Best practices

- **Pilots** (Static). It will include the following information:

a description of the 7 Pop-Machina pilot areas and links to other Pop-Machina website pages that are relevant to each pilot city, visible when someone clicks on ‘Pilots’. Each pilot page will be structured in a similar way and have an exemplary picture of the city centre or another relevant area.

 - Santander
 - Istanbul
 - Venlo
 - Thessaloniki
 - Leuven
 - Kaunas
 - Piraeus

- **Resources** (Regular updates). Divided into:
 - Reports – (deliverable reports, other relevant reports)
 - Dissemination material – this would be split into: leaflet, poster, general Pop-Machina PowerPoint presentation, photo gallery, video(s)
 - Newsletters (also available under “News”)

- Related projects – links to other EU funded similar projects
- **News.** This section is divided into 3 main sections:
 - News – these could be then split respectively into project news and other news
 - Events – These would be then split respectively into: Upcoming Events, Past events and Other events.
 - Newsletters

Contact. General Pop-Machina email account, Pop-Machina Social Media Accounts, if needed: contact persons for the pilot cities

The above-mentioned points constitute a baseline for the website. This will be updated when necessary in order to be in line with the project's requirements and progress. The URL for the website is pop-machina.eu and the contact email for the project is pop-machina@kuleuven.be.

For the monitoring of the website's traffic, the Google Analytics service may be used. This tool provides useful statistics that will help to optimise the website and dissemination strategy. Statistics that will be kept under observation are mentioned in Chapter 6.

5.2.2 Newsletter

A newsletter will be developed bi-annually and issued at the beginning of the new semester (e.g. M7, M13) to report on the previous six months. In total, there will be 7 newsletters plus a final one at the end of the project, if considered necessary.

The newsletter will be primarily distributed to the Network of Interest of the project, but also uploaded to Pop-Machina's website. It will present the project's progress, provide updates on key actions and represent an additional way to inform subscribers about the project's concepts and approaches. Furthermore, the newsletter may be a way to attract and retain stakeholders that are not familiar with social media in order to keep them connected and try to engage them at a later stage.

Although the newsletter will be uploaded to the Pop-Machina website, interested parties will have the option to receive it via email by registering to the newsletter's subscriber list, a process which will take place through a registration form located at the project's website. On top of this, Pop-Machina partners will share the newsletters with their network of contacts, in order to ensure wide outreach.

The newsletters will be prepared by White Research, with the contribution of all partners to specific content when necessary. Mailchimp will be employed for the development and distribution of the newsletter. Although the content of each newsletter will be agreed upon by the partners, in general, the newsletter will mainly include the following sections:

- An introductory section briefly describing the Pop-Machina project
- Progress updates
- A project's news section including articles which will describe the main activities that were carried out during the previous semester
- A section dedicated to future developments (e.g. upcoming events)
- A section listing other relevant major events and/or news
- Other types of relevant articles (e.g. videos, calls to action, etc.)

5.3 Social Media Accounts (SMAs)

The SMAs are valuable tools, which will act as one of the main pillars to frequently promote the project and its ongoing activities. More specifically, a Facebook page, a Twitter account, a LinkedIn account, as well as a YouTube channel were launched in M2, aiming to build an online community of supporters and followers that may continue to exist beyond the duration of the project.

White Research will be responsible for the administration of Pop-Machina's social media accounts. However, all partners are expected to contribute by:

- Becoming a follower (like or follow the page/profile);
- Promoting the accounts in their networks;
- Suggesting relevant profiles that Pop-Machina should connect with;
- Sharing interesting articles and news;
- Promoting posts and news through the social media accounts of their own organisations.

5.3.1 Facebook

A Facebook page was created aiming to build a strong group of followers. This dissemination channel provides an excellent opportunity to share Pop-Machina's news and results among the followers interested in topics that are connected to the project's objectives and activities. More specifically, Pop-Machina's Facebook account will serve as a:

- News and discussion hub where information or news related to the project concepts and approaches will be shared;
- Platform to deliver updates about developments and results of the project (e.g. key events, activities, and important achievements);
- Channel to engage citizens and key target groups by inviting them to participate in the pilots;
- Link to other similar groups and pages associated to relevant and overlapping concepts;
- Additional tool which will collect feedback from users/followers.

Figure 11. Snapshot of Pop-Machina's Facebook page

It is important for the Facebook page to have a consistent flow of information. To achieve this, all partners are required to:

- contribute on a regular basis highlighting relevant news;
- 'like' the Pop-Machina's page;
- 'like' the news and share them with their networks in order to maximise visibility;
- suggest/promote/invite other potential interested users to 'like' the Pop-Machina's page
- contribute to the page with relevant posts and links.

The metrics and insights that are provided by Facebook's analytics will be used to monitor the account's performance.

5.3.2 Twitter

A Twitter account was also launched aiming to build another social community for conveying short messages to followers. Twitter is widely used by all stakeholder groups targeted by Pop-Machina, and thus its use throughout the project can help to steer attention towards the concepts and results of Pop-Machina, identify opportunities for creating synergies with other similar initiatives, as well as enable the effective monitoring of developments and progress in other related projects and relevant organisations.

Twitter is an extremely useful dissemination tool, especially during events in which information needs to be publicised instantly. In particular, the use of hashtags allows messages to reach a wider audience. In the context of Pop-Machina the Twitter account will act as a:

- General dissemination and "heads up" device distributing links that will direct users to other project-related platforms/tools (e.g. Pop-Machina's website, newsletters, videos) and communicating information on project's progress (upcoming events, participation to external events, project results, etc.);
- Newsfeed platform collecting and updating news from other relevant projects and organisations;
- Feedback platform, a fast and easy contact point through which partners could receive queries and feedback from people.

Project partners are expected again to contribute on a regular basis. For monitoring the Twitter's account performance, the metrics and insights provided by Twitter analytics will be used.

Figure 12. Snapshot of Pop-Machina's Twitter account

5.3.3 LinkedIn

A LinkedIn account was set up in order to increase project's visibility within a more professional and institutional channel, which allows the exchange of knowledge and experience among professionals. The LinkedIn page will be dedicated to showcase the project and its objectives, but also to group all Pop-Machina's partners under a single professional page where longer discussions and news/updates will be posted. Besides that, it aims to have a more institutional approach in order to boost professional and expert discussions on issues of common interest and possibly involve large corporations, more start-ups, innovation intermediaries and support networks

Given the professional nature of this social network, the Pop-Machina's LinkedIn page will be more project-focused, hosting content that is either directly related to the project (project's latest news, progress, upcoming events, etc.) or involving wider developments that are expected to have a direct impact on the project (e.g. important reports, changes in legislative frameworks, etc.). Finally, Pop-Machina partners should try to involve followers and third parties in an attempt to initiate professional and expert discussion on issues of common interest.

Figure 13. Snapshot of Pop-Machina's LinkedIn page

The metrics and insights that are provided by LinkedIn will be utilised to keep track and assess the project's performance in this network channel.

5.3.4 YouTube

Finally, the Pop-Machina YouTube channel has been created to gather all videos produced in the frame of the project in a single and easily accessible location, aiming to increase its visibility and bring it closer to the audience by giving faces and voices to the actual participants. However, the aim is not only to have a simple video archive, but also to enhance the creation of a strong online community, thanks to the connection with other similar channels and to leverage the features of videos to effectively promote the project's activities in an appealing and effective way.

The main Pop-Machina promotional video will be produced in M6 in order to raise awareness and create ripple effects that contribute to the project's visibility. Overall, the Pop-Machina YouTube channel will focus on presenting the project's actions and especially the results, showcasing the work of maker communities in the seven pilot areas. Project partners are expected to contribute towards the production of relevant videos (with ideas for the script and actual footage) with a view to build up playlists in the Pop-Machina's channel and share them with the Network of Interest to maximise the outreach.

Figure 14. Snapshot of Pop-Machina's YouTube channel

5.4 Events

5.4.1 Project events

In the frame of Pop-Machina, several events will be organised to serve the project's objectives and promote the project and its outcomes. The following types of events are scheduled as part of the project's plan:

- **“Warm-up” events:** A series of regional **“warm-up”** activities and events such as info-days and meetings (3 events in each pilot city) will be organised at the early stages of the project in order to raise awareness around the Pop-Machina vision, catch the local makers' insights into circular collaborative production and build initial consensus around the project, laying the foundations for the set-up of Pop-Machina's Circular Maker Communities.
- **Workshops:** Several consultation, training, co-creation and policy workshops will be organised in the Pop-Machina Circular Makerspaces throughout the project duration.
- **Co-creation workshops:** two co-creation workshops will be organised in each pilot city, engaging the communities and other stakeholders in a series of co-creative activities to co-design their collaborative production ideas on which the project should focus, as well as co-define the impact assessment framework for their evaluation during the pilot phases.

- **Consultation workshops:** this event will be organised locally in each pilot area in order to facilitate the provision of real-time demand training for the pilot participants. During this workshop, the aim is to co-define the exact process, materials modules and means of training delivery between the communities and educators.
- **Training workshops:** a series of training workshops (physical or virtual) will be organised and will run by M20 with a view to better preparing local communities before they address circular and collaborative manufacturing in the framework of Pop-Machina's pilot operation. All maker communities will be invited to attend and benefit from the workshops. Overall, it is expected that 2 training workshops will be delivered per pilot area with 30 participants in each one. Complementary to the training workshops, the Pop-Machina Circular Maker Accelerator, a 4-month programme, will be organised to offer business, training and mentoring services aimed at getting the pilot projects closer to market.
- **Policy workshops:** ongoing debates and workshops will be organised locally in the pilot cities to share evidence and project's experiences with relevant policy makers and stakeholders, to raise points of attention and highlight possible measures that may help to foster circular community production through Pop-Machina's approaches and tools.
- **Learning workshop:** this event will be implemented in M36 with the aim to share lessons learnt with representatives of Pop-Machina's Network of Interest, and at the same time to serve as the basis for policy recommendations during the upcoming policy debates.
- **Clustering workshops:** these events will be organised throughout the project lifecycle in order to enhance the visibility of the project, and at the same time to explore potential common activities and complementarities with other projects as well as relevant policy initiatives of the EC.
- **Presentation days:** Pop-Machina will organise "Investor Presentation days" in each of the pilot cities to showcase the project's circular productions and draw the attention of industrial stakeholders and investors. By exploring funding opportunities, the presentation days will foster further development and business exploitation of the piloted cases.
- **International Roundtable:** this event will be organised in Brussels towards the end of the project and will be the key policy event of Pop-Machina. Through a dedicated policy roundtable, relevant decision makers will have the opportunity to discuss and validate the policy recommendations of the project on a draft Policy Brief together with regional and national authorities as well as relevant EU Initiatives.

The organisers of the abovementioned events are required to fill in a template (i.e. Event Reporting Template) in which they will present the main communication and/or dissemination action(s) that took place. This template was developed and shared with the consortium in M3.

5.4.2 External events and conferences

Participating in external events and conferences is a unique opportunity to reach audiences with various backgrounds. Throughout the duration of the Pop-Machina project, partners will participate in several industrial exhibitions, trade fairs and conferences that are of interest to the project's stakeholders and revolve around, among others, urban planning, circular economy, sustainable ecosystems and the maker economy in order to:

- present Pop-Machina's concepts;
- stay up to date concerning the latest technological and research findings;
- share knowledge;
- establish contacts and interactions with stakeholders;
- promote Pop-Machina's actions and results';

- overall raise awareness about circular collaborative production.

An initial list of conferences and other events that have been identified is provided through the following table.

Table 6. Indicative external conferences and events

Conference	Date	City	Country
9th Life Cycle Management Conference 2019 http://www.lcm2019.org/	01-04 Sept 2019	Poznan	Poland
EREK International Conference, September 2019: Resource Efficiency in the age of Industry 4.0 https://www.resourceefficient.eu/en/conference	25-26 Sept 2019	Brussels	Belgium
European Days for Sustainable Circular Economy https://edsce19.eu/	30 Sept – 01 Oct 2019	Helsinki	Finland
THE 9th EUROPEAN CONFERENCE ON SUSTAINABLE CITIES AND TOWN http://conferences.sustainablecities.eu/mannheim2020/	30 Sept – 02 Oct 2019	Mannheim	Germany
Circular Design Conference https://www.ecodesigncircle.eu/events/91-circular-design-conference	14 Oct 2019	Barcelona	Spain
19th European Roundtable on Sustainable Consumption and Production – Circular Europe for Sustainability: Design, Production and Consumption (ERSCP 2019) https://erscp2019.eu/index.php	15-18 Oct 2019	Barcelona	Spain
International Conference on Technologies & Business Models for Circular Economy (TBMCE) https://tbmce.um.si/	24-25 Oct 2019	Portorož	Slovenia
3rd International Conference on the Role of Social & Solidarity Enterprises in the Circular Economy https://www.rreuse.org/3rd-international-conference-on-the-role-of-social-solidarity-enterprises-in-the-circular-economy/	06-08 Nov 2019	Berriozar	Spain
Smart City Expo World Congress www.smartcityexpo.com/	19-21 Nov 2019	Barcelona	Spain
ChangeNOW Summit - International Summit for Change www.changenow-summit.com/	30 Jan-1 Feb 2020	Paris	France

Additional conferences and events which relevant with the Pop-Machina project are listed below:

- Raw Materials Summit (www.eitrmsummit.com)
- Maker Faire
- BY&FORCITIZENS (<https://byforcitizens.com/>)
- EIB conference on the Circular Economy

To ensure consistency in the presentation and communication of the project, partners will have at their disposal a leaflet, a template for presentation slides, a standard project presentation, a poster, and a template for publications, all of which will incorporate the Pop-Machina's logo and colours.

Prior to their participation in an external event, the project partners should notify KU Leuven and White Research in timely manner. After partners will have participated in an external event with a key

role (e.g. presenter, discussant, co-organiser, etc.), they will have to report the actions that were carried out and their results, by completing the aforementioned 'Event Reporting Template'.

5.5 Publications

5.5.1 Scientific publications

Scientific publications and conferences are important dissemination channels for sharing Pop-Machina outcomes to academic and industrial target communities, creating knowledge impact and enabling other researchers and stakeholders to use the results in their own work. In particular, a number of scientific publications in leading specialised journals, as well as scientific conferences are foreseen, especially considering the central role of universities in the consortium. It is expected that academic partners will take up the leading role in drafting scientific articles, assisted by all relevant consortium members. These publications could be in relation to project's findings in the fields of urban planning framework and tools, circular collaborative production solutions, sustainable ecosystems, novel impact assessment processes, behavioural science among others or more. An indicative list of journals for the dissemination of scientific outputs is given below:

Table 7. Indicative journals for Pop-Machina

Journal Title	Impact Factor
Journal of Cleaner Production	5.651
Resources, Conservation and Recycling	5.120
Waste Management	4.723
Journal of Environmental Management	4.005
Ecological Economics	3.895
Sustainability Science	3.855
Technological Forecasting and Social Change	3.129
Sustainable Cities and Society	3.073
Cities	2.704
International Journal of Sustainable Development & World Ecology	2.373

Such publications will be useful in order to generate an increased level of awareness and constructive feedback from the scientific community and other relevant project stakeholders. To this end, the first submissions to conferences and papers will take place when substantial scientific results emerge from the project.

Since the Pop-Machina consortium supports open access of scientific publications, all necessary steps will be taken to ensure free access to peer-reviewed articles resulting from the project. Actions in this regard will include the following alternatives as described in the "Guidelines on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in Horizon 2020"³:

- a. **Green open access:** Deposit an electronic copy of the published version or the final manuscript accepted for publication in a scientific publication relating to the project's foreground in an institutional or subject-based repository at the moment of publication. The beneficiaries will make their best efforts to ensure that this electronic copy becomes freely and electronically available to

³http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-pilot-guide_en.pdf

anyone through this repository within 6 months from the publication date. The exact selection of the repository, the terms under which access will be granted, and all other relevant details will be decided when the publication is available.

- b. **Gold open access:** Immediately provide the article in open access mode, with the payment of publication costs being shifted away from readers. The costs (Author Processing Charges) will be paid by the partners supporting the research. Relevant budget is foreseen (to the consortium coordinator) for open access costs regarding two high-impact papers that the consortium will decide that should be freely available immediately after publication.

5.5.2 Non-scientific publications

During the project, all partners will be invited to produce press and media releases, articles in mass media, presentations in TV or radio, or other media. The aim of all these efforts is to increase the project's visibility and publicity, increasing the outreach of the project to stakeholders who may not directly be concerned by it.

In particular, press releases will be produced on an ad-hoc basis, especially when achievements, progress and important actions are achieved or foreseen (i.e. an upcoming event), in order to communicate information proactively to the wider public. General press releases will also be developed, when necessary, targeting stakeholders at the EU level. These press releases will aim to inform stakeholders about the overall project actions and results, but will also incorporate space for featuring specific stories from the pilot cases. Press releases can also be produced prior to each project meeting or project event with the purpose of attracting local media attention.

Besides that, factsheets and infographics may be developed to support communication actions. Their focus will be on general information of Pop-Machina project and its main approaches. In a later stage, as the project progresses and more results are available from the pilot areas, the infographics and factsheets may describe in a concise way the project's outcomes, supporting their communication with visual material.

All partners are responsible for identifying any publishing opportunities and for carrying out all necessary actions to ensure the promotion of project's assets and conclusions. As this will be an ongoing effort by all partners and will depend on occasions that are hardly predictable at this stage of the project, this strategy does not foresee a minimum amount of non-scientific publications. However, track of published material will be kept through the Dissemination Reporting Template on a 6-month basis.

Overall, the main communication and dissemination tools that will be used to reach the different stakeholders targeted by Pop-Machina are summarised in the Table below.

Table 8. Overview of the tools to be used to reach different target audiences

	Cities , Regions & National authorities	Makers / Maker Communities	Industry	Circular Entrepreneurs & Investors	Policy makers	End-users	Academic community	Civil society	General public	Relevant EU projects	Major EU Initiatives
Promotional material											
Logo, leaflet, poster, templates, promotional video, etc.	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Digital presence											
Website	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Newsletter	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Social Media											
Facebook	X	X				X		X	X	X	X
Twitter	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
LinkedIn		X	X	X	X		X	X		X	X
YouTube	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Events											
Warm-up events	X	X	X	X			X	X	X		
Co-creation workshops	X	X	X	X		X	X		X		
Consultation workshops	X	X	X	X		X	X		X		
Training workshops		X									
Policy workshops	X				X			X			X
Learning workshops	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Clustering workshops	X	X		X	X					X	X
Presentation days	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
International Roundtable	X	X			X			X			X
External events	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Publications											
Public deliverables	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Scientific publications					X		X				X
Non-scientific publications	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

6 Monitoring, evaluation and reporting

6.1 Monitoring and evaluation

The implementation of this communication and dissemination strategy will be monitored on an ongoing basis. The frequent evaluation of communication and dissemination actions will allow us to assess their effectiveness and, if necessary, adapt them in order to increase the project's visibility and outreach. White Research is overall responsible for the monitoring and evaluation of Pop-Machina's communication and dissemination activities, although project partners are also expected to help by continuously monitoring/evaluating the publicity and communication actions they carry out.

KPIs will be used as a benchmark to monitor and assess the impact of communication, awareness raising and dissemination activities. Some of the KPIs are provided in the table that follows, together with the target values for M24 and M48. However, these targets might be adjusted at a later stage, based on the experience gathered or additional metrics may be also included. All these metrics will be documented in the updated version of the dissemination and communication plan (M24). Besides the quantitative metrics indicated below, qualitative data will be gathered by eliciting feedback from stakeholders, on all occasions that allow direct contact with them (e.g. events organised or attended).

Table 9. Dissemination plan's targets and indicators.

Assessed element	Metric	M24 Target	M48 Target
Website analytics	Nr. of visits (total)	14000	30000
	Nr. of unique users	7000	15000
	Avg. time spent in website (minutes)	2'	3'
	Nr. of unique pages views	28000	60000
	Bounce rate	50%	50%
SMA analytics	Nr. of followers/likes (total)	700	2000
	Nr. of posts (total)	350	700
	Promotional video	1	1 (+ ad-hoc videos)
	Nr. of views of promotional video	500	1000
Printed materials	Nr. of leaflet copies distributed	1000	2000
Event analytics	Nr. of project events (total/per pilot area)	42/6	72/10
	Attendance rate to project events (total)	980	1600
	Exposure of Pop-Machina in external events (Nr. of events attended/total nr. of people ⁴)	10/1000	30/4000
Newsletters	Nr. of published newsletters	3	8
	Nr. of subscribers	200	500

⁴ Approximation based on event attendance, promotional material distributed, etc.

Assessed element	Metric	M24 Target	M48 Target
Publications	Nr. of published scientific articles	N/A ⁵	12
	Nr. of non-scientific articles for external online and printed sources and/or interviews given	N/A	N/A ⁶
Synergies	Nr. of joint actions with other projects	3	10
Stakeholders reached	Stakeholders reached from project actions ⁷	9500	20500
	Stakeholders reached from external actions ⁸	500	1500
	Total stakeholders reached ⁹	10000	22000

6.2 Reporting

Dissemination reporting is essential to keep track of all the dissemination and communication activities that were carried out. Therefore, partners are expected to continuously report all their actions on a six-month periodic report (M6, M12, M18, M24, M30, M36, M42 and M48) and to contribute to the continuous monitoring of Pop-Machina's dissemination and communication activities.

In order to facilitate the reporting activities on each dissemination and exploitation action undertaken, three documents have been designed and shared with all partners. These include:

Table 10. Monitoring and reporting tools for the dissemination and communication activities

Annex	Dissemination Tool	Coverage	When
2	Dissemination reporting template	All dissemination activities which partners were involved in during the previous 6 months	Every 6 months
3	Event reporting template	Each single event organised or in which partners participate	Within 30 days after any completed event
4	External Conferences and Events template	Any external conference/event that is relevant to Pop-Machina with potential benefit to attend	Throughout the project

During each project semester, all partners are expected to fill in the "Dissemination Reporting template" (Annex 2) reporting all dissemination actions that they carried out during the previous six months.

⁵ The number of scientific articles and papers submitted to conferences will depend on the availability of project results and cannot therefore be estimated for the first half of the project.

⁶ The number of non-scientific articles will depend on several factors; thus, a target will be set in M24, based on the actual project experience

⁷ Organisation of events, project SMAs, project website, newsletter, surveys, interviews, etc.

⁸ Participation in external events, posting articles on external sources of information, etc.

⁹ This metric takes into account the total number of stakeholders who are reached any type of Pop-Machina dissemination action (i.e. both internal and external actions) and through all Pop-Machina communications channels (e.g. website, SMAs, events, publications, etc.).

In addition, for each completed event (workshop, conference, meetings, etc.), partners are required to fill in the “Event Reporting template” (Annex 3) providing information regarding the event that they were involved in. This template should be sent to White Research and KU Leuven within 30 days after the end of the event. Besides that, the event should also be communicated to White Research and KU Leuven in advance for promotional purposes.

The “External Conferences and Events” is an excel file (Annex 4), that partners can fill in each time they identify an event (e.g. conferences, workshops, seminars etc.) relevant to Pop-Machina and in which Pop-Machina partners may be interested in participating in order to promote or present the project. The partners are supposed to share this document with White Research and KU Leuven.

Each project partner should immediately contact White Research in case any risks is identified with regard to communication and dissemination activities or if problems arise during the implementation of publicity actions.

7 Timeline and implementation plan

Communication and dissemination will start from the beginning of the project and will be a continuous process during the project implementation and beyond, as illustrated in Figure 15. However, the communication process is defined in three phases based on the objectives of the project, ensuring that project developments are communicated efficiently and the timing of the stakeholder engagement activities is appropriate. The blend of online and offline communication and dissemination tools and activities is relevant to each phase. The phases are analysed below.

Figure 15. The four stages of dissemination and stakeholder engagement activities

First phase (M1-M6) - Early in the project: Pop-Machina starts to interact and collaborate with its stakeholders in order to enhance the maker community spirit within the local ecosystems of the pilot areas. This phase is focused on the general promotion of the project, putting emphasis on awareness raising, ensuring that the project is appropriately recognised on a wide scale and securing interest and engagement of key stakeholders. The project's visibility will be achieved by: designing the project logo and defining the visual identity, designing and developing the project website, launching the social media profiles of the project, designing and creating the first communication materials. By month 6, all project tools and channels are expected to be in place. Locally, stakeholders will be mapped and informed about the project by using the tools mentioned above. Besides that, a series of "warm-up" events, interviews and the organisation of consultation workshops will bring the targeted communities into a series of co-creative sessions, laying the foundations for the establishment of the "Pop-Machina Circular Maker Communities", as well as the set-up of the "Pop-Machina Circular Makerspaces". The search for a Network of Interest will also be launched in this phase and initial discussions with relevant projects will take place regarding mutual promotional actions and co-organising of events.

Second phase (M7-M35) - During the project: During this phase of the project the technical tools of Pop-Machina will be developed and the operation of the pilots will be planned. In this context, emphasis will be placed on dissemination of the collaborative production tools and the services offered to citizens, encouraging them to participate in the Maker Communities. Stakeholders and involved local communities will provide their constant feedback to enhance the customisation of Pop-Machina's tools in order to further facilitate the operation of the Circular Maker Communities and Makerspaces. Dissemination and engagement activities will be carried out by means of workshops, training programmes and events, in the frame of Pop-Machina Maker Academy, attracting a wider participation of target audiences. Moreover, a series of activities and events will help continue to raise awareness, establish contacts and relations with new stakeholders as well as facilitate knowledge sharing with other similar projects. At the same time, the website and social media accounts will boost the online presence of the project, while Pop-Machina will also leverage other projects and initiatives to create synergies, link with regional and EU-wide stakeholder networks, and enhance its visibility. In M24, an updated version of this strategy will be presented based on the experience gathered by then, which will help devise new actions, if necessary, or adapt planned ones.

Third phase (M36-M48) - By the end of the project: this phase involves the wide and effective dissemination according to the updated DACP, building on the project's favourable reputation and established relationships with the target groups. The Pop-Machina's pilots and their outcomes will be promoted constantly, via online and offline activities. Further engagement to wider audiences will be pursued through publishing and presenting the project's results in external events, conferences and leading scientific journals. The international Roundtable that will be held in Brussels, the development of a Policy Brief and the creation of the "Integration Guide" are some of the most important activities that must be highlighted in this phase. In line with previous efforts towards sustainability and exploitation, the Pop-Machina's consortium will further raise awareness, promote exchange of experiences and knowledge sharing with related initiatives, fostering the uptake of the project results. All findings of the project, the evidence and outputs from the Maker Communities and their tools and services will be disseminated at national and European level to gain more visibility, trust and acceptance for future take-up.

Fourth phase - Beyond the end of the project: the continuous promotion of Pop-Machina and its outcomes, even beyond the project completion, is a key aspiration of the consortium. All partners are expected to continue promoting the project outcomes through their everyday activities, networks and other means. Key stakeholders, who participated in project activities, together with the Circular Maker Communities and Makerspaces are expected to act as multipliers for the adoption of Pop-Machina's results. Finally, publications in popular media together with the scientific papers and the project's reports will further exploit the Pop-Machina development framework. This part of communication and dissemination will be closely intertwined with the activities foreseen under Task 8.3 "Innovation, exploitation, sustainability and replication".

The table below indicates briefly the goals of each phase and the dissemination tools to be used during the respective phase.

Table 11. Dissemination phases, goals of each phase and the respective dissemination tools

Phase	Strategic Goals	Operational objectives	Dissemination tools to be used during the phase
1 st phase (M1-M6)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Raise awareness about the project and its main concepts in relation to the maker movement and circular economy Encourage people to join maker communities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify the target groups Create online and offline tools Announce the project widely 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project logo Project website Project social media Project posters, leaflet, newsletter, presentation, templates Project press release Contact with other projects and networks
2 nd phase (M7-M35)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Raise awareness about the maker movement and circular economy Promote a deeper understanding of the collaborative production and its approaches Empower vulnerable groups Facilitate the adoption of the project's outcomes Introduce the makers movement in the EU's circular economy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Giving visibility to the pilots and their collaborative production tools Encourage further engagement with key stakeholders to motivate their participation in Pop-Machina pilots 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project website Project social media Promotional video Organisation of warm-up events, workshops, presentation days, etc. Participation in third party events Publishing activities (articles, scientific papers, interviews) Press releases and other promotional materials i.e. leaflets in the local languages of the pilot sites focused on the Maker Communities services Newsletters DACP update
3 rd phase (M36-M48)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Raise awareness about the maker movement and circular economy Facilitate the adoption of the project's outcomes Encourage policy makers to embrace collaborative production and circular economy Introduce the makers movement in the EU's circular economy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organisation of the project's dissemination activities to promote findings from the pilot implementation Effective dissemination of the outcomes Support further take-up and exploitation of the project's results Influence decision-making and foster an open policy dialogue 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project website Project social media Organisation of training and learning workshops International Roundtable in Brussels Policy Brief to address specific value chain related issues "Integration Guide" Participation in external events Newsletters Publishing activities (articles, scientific papers, interviews)

An overview of the time plan for the expected usage of the main communication, awareness raising and dissemination tools is presented in the following table.

8 Conclusions

A well-designed communication and dissemination strategy is essential for raising awareness of the project's concept right from the beginning and to implement all the actions needed to exploit the project's outcomes. Therefore, this document outlines all elements that are needed for the communication and dissemination activities planned during Pop-Machina's lifetime and presents the mix of communication channels and actions that will help ensure the maximum visibility of the project and engage with the identified target groups.

Given the bottom-up, open nature of the project and its activities, the dissemination and communication plan will be continuously updated in line with the progress of the project and the needs of the local communities. An updated version of this Dissemination, Awareness raising and communication plan will be delivered in M24, based on the experience gathered during the first 24 months of the project. This will serve to adjust the dissemination approach, where required, in order to increase and improve the outreach to the targeted stakeholders and better convey the project's vision to the European community at large.

Annexes

Annex 1: Pop-Machina initial dissemination and communication guidelines for consortium partners

1 Pop-Machina Dissemination and Communication Guidelines

This document provides you with some key initial guidelines regarding communication and dissemination activities and introduces three main monitoring tools that you are kindly asked to use throughout the project.

1.1 Main guidelines

1. Actively contribute to the dissemination of project results and key messages.
2. Please use the wording “Pop-Machina” to refer to the project; do not use “POP-MACHINA” or “Pop Machina”
3. Please include the project logo, linked to the project’s website, in your electronic signature for all communications that may be relevant to the project.
4. Do not forget to include the EU logo and the disclaimer “Pop-Machina has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 821479”.

In practice, it should look like this:

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 821479

When displayed with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.

You can find the EU emblem in Box or download it in the desired resolution following this link: https://europa.eu/european-union/about-eu/symbols/flag_en.

5. If possible, follow the style guide concerning writing style, formatting options, numbers and currency, abbreviations and acronyms, captions, electronic cross-references, naming conventions, citation style. In general:
 - Use CALIBRI as font for documents generated with MS Office programmes and for web applications. The preferred spacing is 6 pt. before and after paragraph, whereas the preferred line spacing is single
 - Make sure to use the logo colour scheme for documents in order to ensure consistency and to reinforce the visual identity of the project
 - Whenever possible, use the logo lettertype for promotional materials. If in doubt, check with White Research and KU Leuven
 - Always use the same style for references, both for in-text citations and in the bibliography/footnotes
 - Be consistent in using currency references (for example, use EUR instead of € throughout)

- Be consistent in the numbering format; comply with the British usage (e.g. 75,000,239.23), unless differently indicated
 - If you abbreviate a word, use the correct abbreviation (for instance, “m” for million, not “mn”)
 - Make sure to introduce each abbreviation and acronym the first time you use it and create an abbreviation/acronym list at the beginning of the document
 - Review the language and the coherence of the structure of the text you drafted
6. Whenever possible, use the templates that will be provided to you, i.e. letterhead, presentation, publication. A leaflet and a poster will be prepared for you to use throughout the project. Other communication materials (e.g. infographics) will be prepared ad-hoc if needed.
 7. Always inform WR and KU Leuven regarding every dissemination and communication activity that you plan to carry out (e.g. organisation of an event, articles on websites or magazines, participation in an external event, etc.). This will enable us to publicise it through the Pop-Machina communication channels in a timely manner.
 8. You will have to report in detail all the dissemination actions you undertook (please see **Pop-Machina Dissemination Reporting Template** for instructions. This template was sent to all partners by email).
 9. Always report about meetings and events you organised and/or participated in (please see **Pop-Machina Event Reporting Template** for an explanation on how to report about events. This template was sent to all partners by email).
 10. Inform WR and KU Leuven about relevant events (e.g. conferences, workshops, seminars etc.) in which Pop-Machina partners may be interested in participating to promote or present the project. You have received an .xls file named “Pop-Machina_External Conferences and Events”. All partners are kindly requested to fill in this specific .xls file, each time they identify an event relevant to Pop-Machina and share it with WR and KU Leuven.
 11. In compliance with GDPR requirements, **always gather stakeholders’ consent, when collecting, using and storing personal data during events/conferences**. Please consider that pictures which make individuals identifiable are also considered personal data.

The above-mentioned points will be updated when necessary in order to be in line with the project’s requirements and progress.

The Pop-Machina report “**Dissemination and communication plan**” (First version due in M3; Update in M24) includes these guidelines and will also outline the overall project’s dissemination strategy and plan.

1.2 Dissemination monitoring tools

1.2.1 Pop-Machina Dissemination Reporting Template

This is an Excel file that has to be sent **at the end of each project semester** to WR and KU Leuven. All the information required must be provided – the European Commission collects all these data from the Dissemination Manager. Therefore, for each activity please indicate:

- Date
- Place
- Type of activity
- Title
- Type of audience
- Size of audience per type of stakeholder group
- Countries addressed
- Your organisation's role
- Type of material used and quantity (e.g. number of flyers distributed)
- Other partners or external organisation involved
- Short description of action and dissemination activities
- Other comments
- Relevant contacts made (if consent was given).

1.2.2 Pop-Machina Event Reporting Template

The event report has to be sent after every event within **30 days** to both WR and KU Leuven. It is a structured file that includes:

- Event data (title, date, venue, organisers, type and number of attendants, duration)
- Goals and relevance within the project
- Organisation
- Dissemination activities
- Minutes of the events
- Outcomes of the event
- Evaluation
- Annexes (list of participants and scanned copy of the list signed by all participants– if possible, in compliance with the GDPR, agenda, photos, presentations).

2 Website and Social Media use guidelines

2.1 Guidelines for enhancing Pop-Machina online presence

This section provides you with some key initial guidelines regarding your expected contribution and use of the Pop-Machina website and social media accounts (SMAs).

2.1.1 Website

1. Collect photos and videos for all Pop-Machina activities and share them with WR and KU Leuven, so as to make them usable on the website and on the Pop-Machina SMAs.
2. Actively contribute (if possible, with 1 news item per month per partner) to the news section of the website. Please send each news item to WR. A news item can be anything, like a link to other similar projects/activities, an article about a new regulation, a notice regarding a new policy or initiative, an article about an event etc.
3. Inform WR and KU Leuven regarding every event you organise or take part to for the purposes of the project (e.g. conferences, workshops, seminars etc.) and provide WR with a link to the event, so that it can be posted online in the dedicated section of the website.
4. Inform WR and KU Leuven about news articles (e.g. newspaper article, blogpost, TV interview etc.) mentioning your pilot area or the Pop-Machina project and provide WR with a link/scan for giving it more visibility online.

2.1.2 Social media Accounts

1. Register to all Pop-Machina SMAs (i.e. Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube) and use them: monitor announcements and posts, comment, like and retweet.
2. Do make your own posts to foster discussion and keep the page alive.
3. If you would like White Research to publish a post on one or more of the SMAs (e.g. promote an event that is coming up in your city, announce the achievement of a milestone, etc.), please share the post using the dedicated Excel file on Box (“SMA_Scheduled-posts.xlsx” in Pop-Machina/Dissemination and promotion/Social Media).
4. Promote the Pop-Machina SMAs within your network of contacts.
5. Signal to WR relevant profiles that we could follow (on Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn).
6. If you make a short video, edit it so as to enhance the project identity (add the name of the project, the logo, the EU emblem and the disclaimer “This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 821479. The sole responsibility for the content of this video lies with the Pop-Machina project and in no way reflects the views of the European Union.”). WR will take care to upload it on YouTube.

The above-mentioned points will be updated when necessary in order to be in line with the project's requirements and progress.

Annex 2: Dissemination Reporting Template

No. of Action	Date of activity	Place of activity	Type of activity (Choose one of the activity categories listed in the drop-down menu)	Title of conference, workshop, publication, website article, etc.	Type of audience (In case the action reached more than one type of stakeholders please describe this type in the line below. Use as many lines as necessary)	Size of Audience per type of stakeholder group (no. of persons per group)	Countries addressed	Role and description of your organisation's involvement (e.g. facilitator, interviewer, speaker, discussant, author, participant, etc.)	Type of project material used (e.g. Pop-Machina flyer, Pop-Machina poster, project presentation, etc.)	Quantity of project material used (no. of copies distributed per type of project material)	Other Pop-Machina partners or external organisations responsible / involved	Short description of the action as well as of the dissemination activities	Other comments (IF RELEVANT)	Significant contacts made IF RELEVANT (name, position, organisation; if consent to store and share data was given, add also address, tel, fax, e-mail)
1	Example 15/9/2019	Brussels, Belgium	Organisation of a conference	"Title of Conference"	Industry	42	Belgium (50), France (15), Germany (10), Spain (4)	Presenter; Powerpoint presentation of the C4P project	Pop-Machina Presentation	1	N/A	Participation to a conference organised by Organisation X in the thematic area of financing innovative SMEs. We participated as main presenters in a dedicated session. The Pop-Machina poster and flyers were also used during the event. Moreover, important contacts were made with relevant stakeholders.	The participation in the event was successful since the project was introduced to important stakeholders.	1. Contact No. 1 2. Contact No2
					Industry	15								
					General Public	10								
					Policy Makers	12								
2	Example 10/10/2019	Greece	Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication	"..."	Civil Society	1000	Greece	Writer of an article posted on an online newspaper (link)		N/A	N/A	Writer of an article that was posted on a well known Greek online newspaper (link)	The online newsletter is one of the most read websites in Greece.	N/A

Annex 3: Event Reporting Template

1. Event's Aggregate Data

Title	
Date	
Venue	
Organisers	
Audience (number and type)	
Duration	

2. Event's goals, objectives and relevance with Pop-Machina

What were the key objectives of this event/activity? (e.g. to gather ideas, gather data, find new stakeholders, etc.). Was the event relevant to Pop-Machina? To what extent?

3. Organisation of the event

In case of organising a project's event. For participation in external events do not complete this section.

How was the event/activity organized?

- What steps were taken to set up the activity/event?
- What was the location of the event and why was this area selected?

4. Dissemination activities

How was the event/activity promoted? Was project material used for promotion? Was the Pop-Machina project promoted during the event?

5. Structure of the event (short minutes)

Description of the event's sessions.

- What did the event/activity consist of?
- What tools were used? Why were these selected?

For participation in external events, please report what you did at the event.

6. Outcomes of the event

What information or data was gathered as part of this activity? (a brief summary of the information/data gathered is sufficient)

What ideas were generated/What were the main outcomes of the event? (brief explanations are sufficient)

Did you receive any feedback from other participants?

7. Evaluation of the event

What are the main impressions and observation that you made?

- Were there any challenges with this event/activity?
- What were the key successes of this activity?
- If re-deploying this event/activity how will/would you do it differently?

ANNEX: Attachments

- The list of participants (if consent to store and share data was given)
- A scanned copy of the list of participants signed by each participant (if possible)
- The agenda of the event
- Photos (make sure consent was given if individuals are identifiable)
- Presentations (if applicable)
- Copies of materials used to promote the event (e.g. links to press releases, videos, posts, leaflets etc.

Annex 4: External conferences and events templates

No.	Event's name	Thematic Focus	Abbreviation	Date	Location	Registration fees	Deadline for submission	Website	Specific requirements for participation (e.g. abstract submission, ...)	Added by (Partner)
1										
2										
3										